

THE VALUE BASIS OF CHINESE SCHOOL OF MUSICAL PERFORMANCE AND PEDAGOGY MASTERY

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Abstract

In the article, the role of values in the formation and functioning of a music pedagogical school is examined. The thesis is substantiated that the value component bestows stability upon the music pedagogical school and ensures continuity in its development. It is asserted that insufficient attention to the value component hampers the process of forming original music pedagogical schools in China.

Keywords: school of musical performance and pedagogy mastery, national Chinese schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery, values, value approach, musician-performers.

Xu Bo, a Chinese scholar, said that Chinese people "believe that music learning is an essential part of the development of human spirit and a means to upgrade it to the level of national theory: not only in the economic field, but also in the aspect of national authority in the world culture, making China the first in the world" [6, p. 62].

The training of music teachers is carried out within the framework of schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery. School of musical performance and pedagogy mastery is one of the most challenging research objects. Although scholars (S.A. Aisenstadt, Yu. V. Bolotov, A.B. Borodin, A.V. Malinkovskaya, L.G. Sukhova) have discussed the nature and structure of school of musical performance and pedagogy mastery for many times, the model of educational components has not been developed.

In our opinion, the most promising way to understand the phenomenon of music pedagogy is the value approach. The application of this method is in line with the development trend of pedagogy, especially the affirmation of the paradigm of humanism or values. According to this paradigm, any educational phenomenon is based on specific values.

Russian scientists A.B. Borodin [2], A.V. Malinkovskaya [3] have discovered several aspects of school of musical performance and pedagogy mastery. The analysis of their works shows that each of these aspects has a value basis.

It is its tradition to define a school as an educational institution (such as "Gnessin School"). Tradition in turn reflects social values, which are related to the particularity of the interaction between teachers and students within the school and the interaction between the school and the social environment. The existence of such values is very important for Chinese culture. One of the central problems of Chinese culture is the problem of people and society. The social orientation of schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery activities can solve many problems existing in today's Chinese music performance practice, such as the problem that musicians focus on professional development and their own achievements. This hinders musicians' profound understanding of music works and their mission in society (to educate the audience aesthetically

and create conditions for harmonious relationship between people).

As a solid professional foundation in school, the understanding of "handicrafts" at a high level (in the best sense) also has a value component. Excellent performance skills are the basis of high creative achievements in music performance, and are based on personal values, especially the labor values required for high-tech achievements. Direction is not the value of labor, but helps to develop the will quality of the performer and his ability to repeat monotonous actions repeatedly. It is worth noting that these qualities are particularly prominent in Chinese culture.

It is very important to understand that school of musical performance and pedagogy mastery are a solid professional foundation. In fact, many publications believe that the performance skills of Chinese pianists are very high, and they cannot solve complex artistic problems when playing music. Their performances are imitative. A stereotype has been formed among Russian musicians and teachers, that is, the above-mentioned defects lead to the lack of original national school of musical performance and pedagogy mastery in China. In our view, a high level of performance technology is a necessary prerequisite for the formation of any original school of musical performance and pedagogy mastery.

Schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery can also be understood as performing arts and teaching arts. The personal style of one or another musician is first related to specific style directions (romantic school, classical school), and secondly related to theoretical concepts. Systems in the training methods of performers (auditory or psychological technical school, anatomical and physiological school). This aspect of music pedagogy is mainly related to the value of creativity, as well as the value of human personality. In traditional Chinese culture, social values are considered more meaningful than those related to human personality. Therefore, when evaluating the quality of music works, it is often more important to follow the classic and classic models than the original and author's interpretation methods of music works:

- an essential characteristic of the music-pedagogical school is its stability [2; 3; 5]. Continuity serves as a mechanism for establishing the school as a stable

educational entity. Externally, this is evidenced in the transmission of knowledge, abilities, skills, methods, and forms of behavior from the founder of the school to his or her students and followers. An analysis of the works by the aforementioned researchers has led to the identification of factors that enhance the stability of the piano school, which we have categorized as:

- values, attitudes, and ideals, unifying all representatives of the music-pedagogical school;
- traditions, ensuring a connection between different generations of representatives within the school.

The pedagogical component of the music-pedagogical school (principles, methods, forms, techniques, technologies, methodological systems), which objectifies the experience of the school's founder and ensures its transmission both "vertically" (to subsequent generations of students and followers) and "horizontally" (within the scope of national and global music-pedagogical schools);

The codification of the school's experience in material objects - textbooks, educational and teaching-methodological aids, biographical and memoir literature, audio and video recordings.

Among the listed factors, values stand as the leading element. Specifically, they unite all representatives of the music-pedagogical school - the school's leader, students, and assistants, shaping the ideal of performing culture and teaching to which they all orient. Shared values make possible the continuity of schools not only in time but also in space. Currently, many music-pedagogical schools in China act as successors to the Russian music-pedagogical school, owing to their attitude towards beauty in music as an essential spiritual value. Values also underlie the traditions that are formed within a particular music-pedagogical school. For example, the value-oriented approach to a person and their individuality forms the basis of the tradition of collective discussion by the school leader and his or her students of ways of performing musical works, the peculiarities of their interpretation; thereby overcoming the traditional Chinese situation where students merely mechanically follow the instructions of the leader, teacher, or precisely imitate them in the performance of musical pieces.

The analysis of the training practice of Chinese music players (our research involves pianists) shows that schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery pay less attention to the teaching content. However, it is this part that gives the stability of the activities of the Music Education Institute, enabling it to exist for a long time. This is because the teaching principles, methods and forms of teaching and education not only exist in teachers' personal experience (just like the "secret" of music performance), but also exist in textbooks, teaching and teaching methods manuals in an objective form, so that they can be passed on from generation to generation. However, now the teachers of conservatory of music mainly rely on their own student experience and their own experience. This is one of the

reasons why the process of establishing an original national school of musical performance and pedagogy mastery in China is very slow.

From the perspective of pedagogy, the value composition of schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery is very important. Therefore, if a teacher regards the value of "culture" as the primary task, he will not only require students to perform perfectly in technology, but also make efforts to let students understand the cultural background of music creation and how contemporary social and cultural realities affect the way music is expressed. If a teacher's main value is human, he will choose a teaching method that will help reveal each student's personality, focusing not only on teaching tasks, but also on students' personal characteristics and needs. Therefore, the values of schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery and their implementation in the training process of musicians will contribute to the formation of China's national schools of musical performance and pedagogy mastery.

In writing textbooks, educational and teaching-methodological aids, preparing collections of exercises, and audio and video recordings, it is essential that they reflect not only the performance and methodological aspects but also the value component of the music-pedagogical school. This component mirrors the worldview of the school's representatives, their attitude towards music and the musician-performer, towards students, their views on what the process of music education should be like, what is primary in the performance of musical works, what artistic tasks the musician-performer should set for themselves, etc. As a result, the value component of the music-pedagogical school will be transmitted both "vertically" (from generation to generation) and "horizontally" (from region to region, from country to country).

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